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TITLE: Robots are taking over the world! ...or they may just be helping you get to class.

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ABSTRACT

Background: For students with disabilities, accessing education can already be a challenge (i.e., physical barriers - lack of elevators/ramps, inaccessible rooms; content barriers - videos without captions or audio descriptions, inaccessible course websites; attitudinal barriers - stigmatization and discrimination). Telepresence and videoconferencing robots have existed since the late 1990s. A human operator, in a remote location, controls both the videoconferencing component and the mobile base. These robots provide a scaffold for human-to-human interactions. Telepresence robots are different from videoconferencing robots in that they have videoconferencing capabilities on mobile bases. Recent development of affordable telepresence and videoconferencing robots such as Double, VGo, and Beam has allowed use of this technology to spread into school systems across the U.S. Desktop videoconferencing units such as Kubi allow a remote person to control the real-time synchronous communication. However, these robots do not allow for remote controlled mobility of the unit. The person embodied in the desktop videoconferencing robot must rely on others for mobility.

Objective: In this paper we explore the use of telepresence robots on traditional campuses, sharing experiences using this cutting-edge technology in K-12 and postsecondary educational settings and provide best practices and guidelines.

Design/Methods: How this cutting-edge technology is being used in academic settings.

We draw from our research in schools to provide best practices and guidelines for remote students and their peers, educators, and administrators who are using these robots for school attendance. Since both videoconferencing and telepresence robots are being used in academic settings, the guidelines are divided into three sections according to capabilities: 1) videoconferencing (head and neck), 2) mobility (body) for students, and 3) mobility (body) for instructors.

Results: Best Practices and Guidelines

I. Videoconferencing:

- 1) New addition to school; pay attention to how classmates react to the robot

- a. audio—remote student should adjust volume when they change settings.
 - i. the volume used for groupwork should not be the same as the volume used in the classroom
 - b. visual—if the remote student is using a tablet to log in to the robot, the user should place it in a fixed location so classmates are able to ‘see’ the remote student’s face in a consistent way
- 2) Remote user should not share too much personal info--just because the remote student is at home does not mean classmates get to see their home
- a. we recommend the remote student have a classroom ‘corner’ to better control how much classmates can view or hear in the home
 - b. remote student should be classroom ready from the shoulders up—remember classmates can view the user’s face, hair and shirt
 - c. remote student may want to use headphones and a microphone for better audio/visual control
- 3) Socializing; know robot limits—the robot **cannot**
- a. **eat or drink** for the remote student so they will not be able to do this at parties
 - i. if someone is bringing in a special food for class it may be best to avoid this activity.
 - ii. however, students may eat a regular meal (e.g., lunch) at the same time as their friends and socialize as these foods are not typically shared
 - b. **tap someone on the shoulder**—remote students must use their voice or lights to gain attention
 - i. friends may not always be in tune to what the remote student needs so they need to not be shy about using their voice to communicate
 - c. **open doors**—remote students will have to ask people for help on this

II. Mobility—for students

- 1) Personalization: put a t-shirt, dress, buttons, costume - whatever the remote student likes to wear - on the robot
 - a. the robot represents a person
- 2) Walking: Isaac Asimov’s (1950) first law of robotics, ‘a robot may not injure a human being...’ humans always have the right of way, proper yielding is important
- 3) Be an explorer: know how far remote student can go on the WIFI.
 - a. remote student can test drive the WIFI with a buddy and draw a map of the school so the remote student can plot exactly where the connectivity is strongest
- 4) Adjustable height is for standing and sitting so the remote student can make eye contact and participate in class

III. Mobility--for instructors

- 1) Know where they go - X marks the spot: instructor may place an X made out of tape at the remote student’s desk floorspace, so the remote student knows where they ‘sit’ in the class

- 2) Instructors should have a mutually agreed on form of backup communication (e.g., texting, google drive, cell phone, etc.) in case the robot malfunctions and the student loses connectivity

Conclusion(s): There are benefits and limitations of this technology. These robots (Table 1) have been shown to provide promising connectivity for students to be “virtually included” in school. However, these telepresence robots were designed for adults to use in offices and medical settings. VGo and Double are small and about as tall as an elementary school child. VGo was designed to be at the height of a seated adult; Double can change height from seated adult to standing adult. Their height and lightweight (i.e., 15 and 18 lbs. respectively) make them suitable for use in schools. Other telepresence robots like the Beam and BeamPro exist in the worlds of telepresence in offices and hospital settings, but are heavier and at a higher price point, perhaps inappropriate for use in schools. Although Beam has been used some schools, our research has not encountered any Beam robots in our school districts. As such, our best practices and guidelines are drawn from research including the robot models in Table 1. However, these guidelines may be applicable to other human-robot interaction areas with similar robot features, learning tasks, and environments. Our research contributes best practices and guidelines to assist remote students, their peers, and educators in adapting physical, social, and learning environments for virtual inclusion via telepresence robots.

Various robot/vendor options:

Table 1. Kubi, Double, VGo, Beam, BeamPro

Robot Model	Height (inches)	Cost	Fees
Kubi	12”	\$499+cost of iPad	Fees vary
Double	47-59”	\$2499 + cost of iPad	No monthly fee
VGo	48”	\$5000	No monthly fee
Beam	53”	\$2100	No fee for 1 st 3 years
BeamPro	63”	\$15,000	No fee for 1 st 3 years

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